

Learning Design Brief Template

FOR LEARNING RESOURCES

What is the Learning Design Brief?

The Learning Design Brief is a collaborative planning tool that helps create learner-centred resources by aligning them with desired outcomes to engage key audiences and support effective learning.

We suggest using it *before* resource creation. The template can also be used for the reviews of developed resources.

Why consider incorporating Learning Design at this point?

<p>Reduce barriers to entry</p> <p>User-centred resources make learning easier and encourage use of other tools and platforms the learning resources support</p>		
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How to use this template

- 1) Use the template as a planning document before you create a resource.
- 2) Use the template to guide design conversations with the Skills team - a shared understanding of learner requirements enables effective co-development of the learning resource.

*Items marked with a * are essential questions (page 5). We recommend considering these before discussing the brief with the ARDC Skills Team.*

What might co-development look like?

Clarifying design intentions and understanding how the resource is received helps the development of fit for purpose, learner-centred resources. To achieve this, there is usually some work involved both before (Stages 1,2) and after (Stages 5, 6) the creation of the resource.

Please note that draft materials shared during co-development are not to be used, due to the risk of misrepresentation. Final versions may be used, provided the ARDC is properly acknowledged.

Note: Resource design is often iterative and might not always follow the sequence above.

Learning Design Brief

REQUEST DATE	REQUESTED BY	REQUESTER NAME (NAME OF ORGANISATION IF NOT ARDC)
	<input type="checkbox"/> ARDC <input type="checkbox"/> Project partners	

ARDC CONTEXT	
This resource is linked to: <input type="checkbox"/> HASS & I RDC <input type="checkbox"/> Planet RDC <input type="checkbox"/> People RDC <input type="checkbox"/> Other: (add details)	How does this resource fit within the ARDC strategy? State any related ARDC Thematic Research Data Commons, programs and/or projects.

LEARNING DESIGN REQUEST
Is the request for....? <input type="checkbox"/> Co-development of learning resources <input type="checkbox"/> Review of developed learning resources <input type="checkbox"/> Other : (add details)_____

TITLE OF TRAINING PACKAGE OR RESOURCE
This title is indicative only and can be changed on completion of the project.

BACKGROUND
Please provide a brief description of the drivers for developing the resource.

*INTENDED AUDIENCE
Who is the training resource for? Select all that apply.

<input type="checkbox"/> Government <input type="checkbox"/> Industry <input type="checkbox"/> Higher Degree Researchers (HDRs) or PhD candidates <input type="checkbox"/> Early Career Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Mid-late Career Researchers	<input type="checkbox"/> Infrastructure providers (including research facilities) <input type="checkbox"/> Digital skills trainers <input type="checkbox"/> Data custodians and/or data managers <input type="checkbox"/> Others (Please specify): _____
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***PURPOSE(S) and OBJECTIVES**

Why does the audience need this training resource? What will the audience learn from it?

***CONTEXTS**

To avoid duplication of effort, have you checked to see if there are any similar resources available?

Yes
 No

Please provide link(s) and details to similar, existing resources. Explain how the developed resource adds to the existing content.

Select relevant guidelines that apply to the developed resource.

Style guidelines
 Technical requirements (E.g: Compatibility with specific systems)
 Identified curriculum (please provide the relevant documents)
 Policies, standards, frameworks
 Other (Please specify): _____

PREREQUISITES

What prior skills or prior knowledge might the audience need to be able to use the developed resource?

Unsure
 No prior skills or knowledge needed
 The developed resource assumes that the audience has skills or knowledge in the following areas:

- (Please state)
- (Please state)
- (Please state)

EXAMPLES

Examples of prior skills:

- Basic R programming skills
- Create and use a key pair

Example of prior knowledge:

- A basic understanding of what the Nectar Cloud is
- Know how to log in to the Nectar Virtual Desktop
- Recognise and identify the data types: integer, float, string
- Describe a key pair

LEARNING OUTCOMES	
<p>Please outline outcome statements that capture what knowledge, skills and competencies learners should be able to specifically demonstrate following use of this training material/resource.</p> <p><i>(The Skilled Workforce team at the ARDC are able to help with the identification of Learning Outcomes, if needed.)</i></p>	<p><u>EXAMPLES</u> Example Learning Outcomes: <i>By the end of this session, learners should be able to:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Log in to the Nectar Virtual Desktop • Manage (reboot, shelve, delete, boost) their desktop • Complete general tasks and maintenance

DELIVERABLES		
FORMAT	<p>Is a “Train-the-trainer container” needed?</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	<p><i>A Train-the-trainer container could include the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training package implementation guide • Learner materials • Facilitator guide • Assessment tools (E.g: Tests, quizzes, feedback surveys, practical demonstrations) <p><i>*To be determined on a case by case basis</i></p>
*RESOURCE TYPE	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Guide</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Infographic</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Poster</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Slide deck</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Decision tree/ flowchart</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Summary document (1 pager)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> FAQ</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Other</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping document • Facilitator guide • Assessment tool • Self-assessment tool • Activities and exercises • Other (pls specify) • Unsure

EXAMPLE ONLY

Milestones Timeline

Please let us know of any deadlines or milestones you have in mind.

MILESTONES	INDICATIVE TIMELINE
*Final versions of deliverables shared	
Finalisation of Learning Design Brief	
Creation of draft resource	

**Final versions of project deliverables or source materials must be submitted before Learning Resources can be drafted, to ensure accuracy and avoid the risk of misrepresentation.*

HOSTING PLATFORM
Where will the final Learning Resource be hosted? <input type="checkbox"/> ARDC webpage <input type="checkbox"/> Partner webpage <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <u> (add details) </u>

ADDITIONAL SERVICES	
Does the resource require graphic design and/or other special service (e.g. video editing, captioning) before publishing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unsure	Who will be providing these services?

BEING 'FAIR'
Have you considered applying FAIR To your training materials? The ARDC Training Materials Metadata checklist helps enable sharing and reuse of your training materials.

LICENSING	ATTRIBUTION
Include licensing details, e.g., Creative Commons 4.0 International Attribution Licence . Consider checking your institution's Intellectual Property Policy to ensure you have the right to do this. *Applying a CC-BY-4.0 licence allows anyone reusing the work to re-use it widely as long as they attribute the creator.	Include preferred citation for the resource. See How to attribute an ARDC project investment for guidance.

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DReSA
Digital Research Skills Australasia (DReSA) is a digital platform which helps learners, trainers, and training providers discover digital research skills-focused educational events and resources. Please let us know if you would like to share this resource on DReSA. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, I am happy to share this resource, if suitable, on DReSA. <input type="checkbox"/> No, I have concerns about sharing this resource on DReSA.

KEY STAKEHOLDERS	CONTACT DETAILS
Include subject matter experts and content providers	

COMMENTS
Please add in any further details or comments that are applicable to the production of your learning resource.

REVIEWS	DATE
<u>Content Review</u> Include names of reviewers	DD/MM/YYYY
<u>Learning Design Review</u> Include names of reviewers	DD/MM/YYYY

The Learning Design Brief is informed by the following Universal Design for Learning (UDL) resources:

- [Universal Design for Learning \(UDL\)](#), developed by CAST
- [Universal Design](#) by [the Centre for Universal Design Australia](#)
- NSW Government's [Universal Design for Learning planning tool](#)
- [Universal Design for Learning in Tertiary Education](#)

References:

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Clapper, T. C. (2015). Cooperative-Based Learning and the Zone of Proximal Development. *Security Dialogue*, 46(2), 148–158. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878115569044>

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Sweller, J., Ayres, P., & Kalyuga, S. (2011). *Cognitive Load Theory (1st ed.)*. Springer New York.

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Wiggins, G. P., & McTighe, J. (2006). Backward Design. In *Understanding by Design (Expanded 2nd ed., pp. 13-34)*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.